

MODERN APPROACHES TO THE TREATMENT OF IRON DEFICIENCY ANEMIA IN ADOLESCENT GIRLS

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Abstract. *Diagnosis and correction of iron deficiency conditions remain a pressing issue in practical pediatrics. The article presents data on the prevalence and characteristics of clinical manifestations, diagnosis and treatment of iron deficiency in adolescents. The special significance of diet and the importance of choosing the right iron-containing drug for correcting iron deficiency in adolescents are noted. Iron deficiency states (iron deficiency anemia (IDA) and latent iron deficiency (LID)), according to the World Health Organization (WHO, 2003), rank first among the 38 most common human diseases. It is known that IDA and LID affect more than 3 billion people on Earth. Studies conducted in different countries of the world show differences in the prevalence of iron deficiency states depending on the age, gender, and socioeconomic conditions of the country. Children, especially those in their first two years of life, teenage girls, and women of reproductive age are at risk for developing iron deficiency. Adolescents should be singled out among the risk groups, since they have several reasons for an increased risk of developing iron deficiency states. Firstly, insufficient iron intake with food: an unbalanced diet lacking sufficient meat products (vegetarianism), weight-loss diets, etc. Secondly, adolescents have increased iron requirements due to accelerated growth rates (puberty growth spurt). Thirdly, this age group is characterized by various diseases accompanied by increased iron losses – helminthic and parasitic infestations, erosive and ulcerative diseases of the stomach and duodenum, frequent nosebleeds, injuries, surgeries, heavy menstruation, etc. Iron deficiency, both obvious and hidden, has negative consequences for the child's health. Iron is a part of not only heme, but also of many enzyme systems of the body (enzymes of systemic and cellular aerobic metabolism, oxidation-reduction homeostasis). A decrease in the amount of iron in the body (in tissue depots, blood serum, bone marrow) leads to a disruption in the formation of hemoglobin and the development of hypochromic anemia, as well as the occurrence of trophic disorders in various tissues.*

Keywords: *iron deficiency, iron deficiency anemia, pediatrics.*

Relevance. Iron deficiency in children contributes to delayed physical, neuropsychic, and sexual development, cognitive impairment, provokes the development of chronic fatigue syndrome, immunological deficiency, disrupts the functioning of endocrine glands, and increases the absorption of heavy metals, especially lead. Despite the fact that adolescents are at risk for developing iron deficiency, IDA is rarely diagnosed in them, which is primarily due to the nonspecific nature of the clinical manifestations of iron deficiency. Clinical manifestations of iron deficiency include pale skin and mucous membranes, trophic disorders of hair and nails, angular stomatitis, taste perversion, addiction to unusual odors, muscle weakness, asthenovegetative manifestations, and increased incidence of viral infections. Detection of such symptoms in an adolescent should make the doctor suspect iron deficiency, which requires a series of laboratory tests to confirm.

A classic laboratory sign of anemia is a decrease in hemoglobin concentration, then the number of erythrocytes and the hematocrit value. According to WHO recommendations (2001), the lower limit of the norm for venous blood hemoglobin is 115 g / l in children 6-11 years old and 120 g / l in children over 12 years old. To confirm the iron deficiency nature of the identified anemia, it is necessary to determine the indicators of the iron transport fund: the level of serum iron, the total iron-binding capacity of the serum, the transferrin saturation coefficient, and the level of serum ferritin. Determination of these indicators is also necessary if the presence of IDA is suspected. WHO recommends using biochemical criteria for the diagnosis of IDA. Determination of the level of serum ferritin is one of the optimal methods for assessing the content of iron reserves. Regardless of age, the criterion for depletion of tissue iron stores is considered to be a serum ferritin level below 10–12 µg/l. Other laboratory parameters are also widely used to diagnose iron deficiency conditions: color index, hematocrit, mean corpuscular hemoglobin content, mean corpuscular hemoglobin concentration, mean corpuscular volume, anisocytosis index, zinc protoporphyrin, reticulocyte indices, and latent iron-binding capacity of serum.

The purpose of this study. Subsequently, dynamic monitoring of the children's health, drug tolerance, and laboratory studies to assess the effectiveness of therapy were carried out. The importance of active detection of iron deficiency states among the Boarding School students is associated with several aspects. The Boarding School students belong to the risk group for developing iron deficiency according to many criteria (adolescence, intensive growth, establishment of menstrual function, the presence of frequent dysfunctional uterine bleeding). In the treatment of iron deficiency states, it is necessary to adhere to two main directions: influencing the cause that led to the development of this pathology, and replenishing the iron deficiency with medicinal iron-containing preparations [20]. To eliminate the cause of iron deficiency, it is necessary to treat background diseases (eliminate sources of blood loss, digestive disorders, helminthic invasions, etc.). Since one of the main causes of iron deficiency in adolescents is the alimentary factor (insufficient iron intake with food), it is necessary to take measures to correct the patient's diet (increase meat consumption as the main food product containing iron).

Materials and methods of research. The main amount of iron (~90%) is absorbed in the duodenum, the rest – in the upper parts of the jejunum. The amount of iron received during the day with food is approximately 10–12 mg (heme in combination with non-heme), but only a tenth of it (1–1.2 mg) is absorbed in the intestine of a healthy person. In iron deficiency, the absorption surface of the small intestine increases. It has been established that the bioavailability of heme iron in food products is higher than that of non-heme compounds and is 25–30%. The sources of heme iron are hemoglobin and myoglobin in animal products (meat and poultry). Non-heme iron is contained in plant products (vegetables, fruits, cereals), as well as in milk and fish. Recommended iron intake levels take into account the physiological needs of the body and the average bioavailability of iron from a normal diet, which does not exceed 10%. Dietary recommendations are an important addition to drug correction of sideropenia.

The correct choice of iron preparation, its dose and duration of treatment for correction of iron deficiency conditions in adolescents is the key to treatment effectiveness. It is important not only to choose the right preparation, determine the duration of its administration, but also to take into account all possible side effects. The most important requirements for oral iron preparations used in pediatric practice are good bioavailability, high safety, the availability of various dosage forms convenient for patients of all ages, as well as characteristics that ensure good adherence to

treatment. Numerous studies conducted in our country and abroad show that the preparation of iron (III) hydroxide-polymaltose complex (Maltofer) meets these requirements to the greatest extent. Due to the optimal combination of iron with polymaltose, the mechanism of action of the preparation is such that an overdose and the development of associated oxidative stress are practically impossible.

According to a meta-analysis of six randomized controlled trials, iron (III) hydroxide polymaltose is better tolerated than iron salt preparations and causes fewer adverse effects than iron (II) sulfate. The high efficacy of therapy with iron (III) hydroxide-polymaltose complex preparations has been confirmed, in particular, its effect on cognitive function in schoolchildren suffering from IDA. The studies by P.B. Devaki et al. (2009) showed the effect of iron (III) hydroxide polymaltose therapy on memory and intelligence indices in adolescents with IDA. In addition to its proven efficacy and good tolerability, iron (III) hydroxide polymaltose is easy to use for patients, which is especially important for adolescents, as it increases adherence to therapy and, consequently, its efficacy. Iron (III) hydroxide polymaltose preparations are available in various dosage forms for different age groups.

The therapeutic dose of iron (III) hydroxide-polymaltose complex preparations is 5 mg/kg per day. The daily dose can be divided into one or two doses. The duration of the course of treatment of iron deficiency anemia with iron preparations is from 2 to 5 months depending on the severity of the anemia: for mild anemia - 2 months; for moderate anemia - 3-4 months; for severe anemia - 4-5 months [31]. To correct latent deficiency, the iron preparation is prescribed in half the dose of 2.5 mg/kg per day, while the duration of the prophylaxis course is 8 weeks (or in the full therapeutic dose of 5 mg/kg of body weight per day - 4 weeks). Thus, the diagnosis, treatment and prevention of iron deficiency in adolescents have features that must be taken into account by practicing pediatricians. In addition, adolescents are at risk for developing iron deficiency conditions for a number of reasons, which is why the development of new screening programs for iron deficiency conditions in adolescents for the purpose of timely diagnosis and treatment is an urgent task.

Currently, oral iron preparations are divided into two main groups: ionic and non-ionic (the latter are represented by protein and hydroxypolymaltose complex of trivalent iron).

Ionic preparations are represented by salts of divalent iron, including iron sulfate (ferrofol, tardiferon, ferroplex, sorbifer, ferro-folgamma, etc.); iron chloride (hemofer); polysaccharide compounds - gluconate-fumarate combinations (heferol, ferronal, megaferrin). Divalent iron chelates (citrate, lactate, gluconate, succinate) are absorbed better than iron sulfate. In case of intolerance to salt preparations of divalent iron, which are currently the most effective in the treatment of anemia and replenishment of iron stores, it is possible to use non-ionic preparations of trivalent iron in the form of a hydroxypolymaltose complex (maltofer, biofer, ferrum lek, etc.).

When choosing a drug and the optimal dosage regimen, it is necessary to remember that an adequate increase in hemoglobin levels in IDA can be ensured by the intake of 30 to 100 mg of divalent iron. Considering that with the development of IDA, iron absorption increases by 25-30% (with normal iron reserves in the body - only 3-7%), 100 to 300 mg of divalent iron per day are prescribed. The use of higher doses does not make sense, since iron absorption does not increase. The absorption rate of divalent iron salts is several times higher than that of trivalent iron, so drugs containing divalent iron provide a quick effect and normalize hemoglobin levels on average in 1–2 months, and normalization of iron levels in the depot occurs in 3–4 months from the start of

treatment and depends on the severity of anemia and the dose of the drug. Longer use of drugs containing iron in the trivalent state is required; in case of copper deficiency in the body, they will be ineffective. Normalization of hemoglobin levels during treatment with a trivalent iron drug will occur only in 2–4 months, and replenishment of iron deficiency in the depot - in 5–7 months from the start of therapy. The degree of absorption is also reflected in the frequency of side effects. The undesirable effect of solid forms of iron preparations (tablets, encapsulated) on the gastrointestinal mucosa can be reduced by taking them during meals, but this reduces the absorption of iron. When taking the drugs in a sufficient dose, an increase in the number of reticulocytes is observed on the 7-10th day from the start of treatment. Normalization of the hemoglobin level is noted in 3-4 weeks after the start of treatment, and in some cases, it is delayed up to 6-8 weeks. The total duration of treatment depends on the initial severity of anemia. Standard terms of ferrotherapy of IDA: for mild severity - 4-6 weeks, for moderate severity - 8-12 weeks, for severe - 16 weeks or more. Against the background of the use of ferropreparations orally, the most common side effects are nausea, vomiting, anorexia, constipation (due to iron binds hydrogen sulfide, which is a physiological stimulator of motility), less often - diarrhea, metallic taste in the mouth, black staining of the mucous membranes and teeth, allergic reactions, headache. These side effects lead to frequent refusals of treatment by patients. The bioavailability of divalent iron salts is several times higher than that of trivalent iron salts, as they freely diffuse through DMT1 protein channels and ferroportin. The pharmacological effect of the drugs is rapid, and the normalization of hemoglobin levels occurs on average in 2 weeks to 2 months, and replenishment of iron stores occurs after 3-4 months from the start of treatment, depending on the severity of anemia and the dosage of the drug. In this regard, WHO recommends divalent iron preparations as a starting therapy for iron deficiency anemia. The absorption of ions from trivalent iron preparations is slower, since active (energy-dependent) transformation with the participation of ferroxidases is necessary. Therefore, such drugs require longer use, and in case of copper deficiency in the body, they will be ineffective at all.

Researches and discussion. The contingent of students of the Boarding School consists of more than 700 girls aged 10-18 years. In order to screen for iron deficiency conditions among the students of the Boarding School, a clinical blood test is conducted during the annual medical examination. A hemoglobin level below 120 g/l is considered anemia; an indirect sign of latent iron deficiency is a combination of reduced erythrocyte indices (MCV, mean corpuscular volume, MCH, mean corpuscular hemoglobin) and a color index (below 0.85) with a normal hemoglobin level. Data on the prevalence of IDA and LDH among students of the Boarding School are presented. All pupils who showed signs of iron deficiency during the medical examination were recommended to undergo additional laboratory tests - a biochemical blood test to determine the level of serum iron, iron-binding capacity of the blood serum, and ferritin levels, after which therapy with iron preparations was prescribed.

REFERENCES

1. Rasulova, N., Abdullaev, K., & Kuddusova, K. (2024). THE INTEGRATED APPROACH TO THE TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH ATROPHIC RHINITIS WHO HAVE COVID-19. *Science and innovation*, 3(D7), 56-60.
2. Abdullajanov, B., Botirov, A., Akhmadbekov, B., Bozorov, N., & Khamidov, F. (2024). ENDOSCOPIC METHODS OF HEMOSTASIS AND SURGICAL TACTICS FOR

- ULCERATIVE GASTRODUODENAL BLEEDING IN THE ELDERLY (LITERATURE REVIEW). *Science and innovation*, 3(D7), 21-31.
3. Kuziev, D., Aliev, A., & Zokirova, A. (2024). FEATURES OF THE COURSE OF SEVERE PNEUMONIA IN CHILDREN UNDER ONE YEAR OF AGE AGAINST THE BACKGROUND OF INFECTIOUS TOXICOSIS. *Science and innovation*, 3(D7), 4-8.
 4. Khaitbaeva, N. (2024). RESISTANCE INDICATORS OF WHEAT AND RICE VARIETIES TO FUSARIUM WILT IN THE CONDITIONS OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN. *Science and innovation*, 3(D7), 69-72.
 5. Yakubov, X., Kuziyev, O., Kodirov, Q., & Kurbonov, A. (2024). SECTIONAL BRAIN STUDY. *Science and innovation*, 3(D5), 501-505.
 6. Khamroeva, Y., & Erkinova, O. (2024). Analysis of the results of treatment of secondary glaucoma in children associated with retinopathy of premature. *Science and innovation*, 3(D7), 113-116.